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3 **Title:** Inter- and intraspecific diversity of ontogeny and fecundity patterns in relation to
4 reproductive strategy choice in Myomorpha (Rodentia: Calomyscidae, Cricetidae, Muridae)

5 **Running title:** Characterization of pre- and postnatal development in Myomorpha

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49 care and use of animals were followed. All procedures performed in this study involving animals
50 were in accordance with the ethical standards of Ferdowsi University of Mashhad.

51

52 **Author contributions**

53 KH designed the study, collected the samples and conducted laboratory procedures, wrote the
54 manuscript and provided the figures. MMM conducted the methodology and inferences, and also
55 had valuable discussions about the content. JD conceived and designed the study, and also
56 stimulated the interest in brush-tailed mice study. VGM had valuable discussions about the
57 content. All authors contributed in proofreading.

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63 **Inter- and intraspecific diversity of ontogeny and fecundity patterns in relation to**
64 **reproductive strategy choice in Myomorpha (Rodentia: Calomyscidae, Cricetidae,**
65 **Muridae)**

66

67 **Abstract**

68 Studying the life history of various organisms is essential for ecological and evolutionary
69 inferences. However, publications regarding models of evolutionary shifts to either *r*- or *K*-
70 reproductive strategies are scarce. Here, the combined original and previously published data on
71 reproduction and development of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*),
72 golden hamster (*Mesocricetus auratus*), and house mouse (*Mus musculus*) were compared. An
73 adult male and female in estrous state (from each species) were coupled with each other for a
74 night and embryos were harvested at embryonic days (E) 10-17 from pregnant females. The
75 mean gestation period in Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse was 31.5 ± 2.1 days, growth was rapid at
76 the first half of this period and after that it was reduced by half. During the postnatal period,
77 growth was rapid up to weaning, but after day 35, the rate of growth decreased abruptly. Growth
78 rate of head and body length was very rapid prior to weaning (PN35) in comparison to weight
79 but the rates of the two characters were inversed following weaning. Totally, weight gain was
80 more dynamic in rate, as compared with head and body length, up to adulthood. For golden
81 hamster and house mouse, gestation period were 15.6 ± 0.8 and 20.8 ± 0.8 days, respectively.
82 Growth was slow during approximately the first half of the gestation period in both species but
83 increased during the second half. During postnatal period in golden hamster, growth rate of head
84 and body length was rapid both before and after weaning as compared with that of weight.
85 However, head and body length showed a stable rate of growth before and after weaning (around
86 PN15), but for body weight, the growth rate was slightly faster after weaning. Similarly, changes
87 in head and body length in house mouse were rapid both before and after weaning (PN16) as
88 compared with that of weight. Since approximately two times increases were observed in the
89 growth rates of weight and head and body length in the second stage of postnatal development
90 (PN16-adult) compared with the rates during the first stage (PN0-PN16), both showed dynamic
91 changes during the postnatal development in this species. Typically *r*-strategic house mouse
92 appeared to be more similar in early morphological development to comparatively *K*-strategic
93 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, than to comparatively *r*-strategic golden hamster. Nevertheless,

94 growth rate and pattern were different in the three species after birth. Hence, results showed that
95 peculiarities of association between an ontogenetic pattern and a tendency in reproductive
96 strategy can differ in diverse groups of myomorph rodents.

97

98 **Keywords** Ontogeny. Pre- and postnatal development. Reproductive strategy. *Mus*.
99 *Mesocricetus*. *Calomyscus*. Arvicolini

100

101 **Introduction**

102 Traditional scenarios of higher vertebrate evolution are most often based on assessment of
103 similarities in adult morphology of living and fossil forms. However, the basic approach of
104 “evolutionary developmental biology (*Evo-Devo*)” is that evolutionary changes are the result of
105 ontogenetic pathways rather than changes occurring after birth (Creighton and Strauss 1986;
106 Eilam 1997; Wilson 2011). Although several studies have documented the variability and
107 evolution of ontogenetic allometry (Fadda and Leirs 2009), heterochronic patterns (Weston
108 2003; Cubo et al. 2006; Zollikofer and de León 2010), or growth patterns among species and
109 intraspecific clades (Cardini and O’Higgins 2005; Marroig 2007; Wilson and Sánchez-Villagra
110 2010) in mammals, all have focused on the postnatal period of development. Early ontogenetic
111 stages have been ignored despite their important role on adult state (Bastir and Rosas 2004;
112 Bulygina et al. 2006; Wilson et al. 2008; Wilson and Sánchez-Villagra 2010).

113 In mammals the relationship between pre- and postnatal development as well as the evolutionary
114 role of prenatal ontogeny are limited to studies of humans and other primates (e.g. Bastir and
115 Rosas 2004; Vinicius 2005; Sardi et al. 2007). One reason for this is the difficulty in obtaining
116 prenatal series for any mammal with the sample size required to assess precise relationships
117 (Sánchez-Villagra 2010). This is particularly acute with rodents in which it is difficult to obtain
118 embryos at early stages of prenatal development due to the small size of the embryos. For this
119 reason, precise determination of conception is needed but is extremely difficult to obtain.
120 However, comprehensive data on reproduction and/or comparative ontogenesis are available
121 (Asdell 1946; Creighton and Strauss 1986; Hayssen et al. 1993; Eilam 1997; Kaufmann and Bard
122 1999; Kaufmann 2008; Olio et al. 2014) which makes it possible to model evolutionary events,
123 including shifts in reproductive strategy.

124 Life history studies explain how organisms adapt to achieve reproductive success. The major
125 features of life history are age-structured reproduction and survival including age and size at
126 maturity, length of reproductive lifespan, reproductive investment, mean fertility and aging
127 which can be influenced by changes in the environment such as resource availability and
128 environmental fluctuations (Stearns 2000; Reznick et al. 2002; Dobson and Oli 2008). Pianka
129 (1970) mentioned some elements to distinguish two main groups of life histories known as
130 Pianka's correlates of *r*-selection and *K*-selection including climate, population size, inter- and
131 intraspecific competition, relative abundance, and longevity. Ontogenetic variations observed
132 among species (or higher taxa) are cues leading to understanding life history traits, often based
133 on some characteristics such as rapid development, short-lived, and high fecundity (*r*-strategy)
134 versus slow development, long-lived, and low fecundity (*K*-strategy). Therefore, the *r*- or *K*-
135 strategies are known to be two opposite adaptive scenarios of survival (Dobzhansky 1950;
136 MacArthur and Wilson 1967; Reznick et al. 2002).

137 In reality no organism is completely “*r*-selected” or completely “*K*-selected” but all must reach
138 some compromise between the two extremes (Pianka 2000). According to Fisher (1930), “it
139 would be instructive to know not only by what physiological mechanism a just apportionment is
140 made between the nutriment devoted to the gonads and that devoted to the rest of the parental
141 organism, but also what circumstances in the life history and environment would render
142 profitable the diversion of a greater or lesser share of the available resources towards
143 reproduction”.

144 The house mouse, *Mus musculus* Linnaeus, 1758 (Rodentia: Muridae) is the most common
145 model system for mammalian development (Zelditch et al. 2003b). This species displays a
146 typical *r*-reproductive strategy, being able to produce tremendous outbreaks of population
147 density (Weber and Olsson 2008). The golden or Syrian hamster, *Mesocricetus auratus*
148 (Waterhouse, 1839) (Rodentia: Cricetidae), another animal model, is easy to breed in captivity,
149 so it is used in laboratories for broad fields of research (Valentine et al. 2012). The laboratory
150 stocks of this species can display a typically *r*-kind of reproduction. Although no evidence of
151 population explosions have been reported in the wild, they are considered a major agricultural
152 pest within their native range and are subjected to extensive annual exposure to rodenticides
153 (Gattermann et al. 2001) which appears to have resulted in population declines (Yigit and
154 Kryštufek 2008). Brush-tailed mice (Rodentia: Calomyscidae) are a group of small-sized rodents

155 found in rocky outcrops and semi-mountainous areas in desert regions of Syria, Azerbaijan, Iran,
156 Turkmenistan, Afghanistan and Pakistan (Musser and Carleton 2005; Kilpatrick 2017). With a
157 mouse-like exterior and ecotype, that appears to be a common morphology of rodents, brush-
158 tailed mice are known to have a life span of over 9 years in captivity (Volf and Volf 2003),
159 second only to the slender-tailed cloud rat, *Phloeomys cumingi* (Waterhouse, 1839) which is
160 reported to have a maximum lifespan of 13 years in captivity (Denys et al. 2017). These rodents
161 are also characterized by comparatively slow rate of postnatal development and low fertility rate
162 (Meyer and Malikov 1996; Kilpatrick 2017). There are no data on prenatal life history of this
163 group and the only embryology reference is Hamidi et al. (2017b).

164 The aim of the present study was to describe changes in growth and development which take
165 place during pre- and postnatal stages of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*
166 Goodwin, 1939) in comparison with the house mouse and the golden hamster. For this purpose,
167 the following items were considered: 1) comparative stages of pre- and postnatal development in
168 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, house mouse, and golden hamster, and 2) the fecundity in
169 laboratory stocks of the three species as well as some voles including their ontogenetic and
170 reproductive extremes which were "pulled out" from the "bottle-necked" origins of captive
171 breeding colonies. Most laboratory stocks originated from very few parental individuals and
172 hence, the effects of inbreeding are inevitable. In such situations some characteristics (for
173 example, alternative reproductive parameters to those observed in wild populations) which are
174 hidden by genetic polymorphism of natural populations, can be revealed (Meyer and Malikov
175 1996; Olenev 2002).

176

177 **Materials and Methods**

178 **Animal capture and breeding**

179 The Goodwin's brush-tailed mice (12 adult males and 15 adult females, average weight 19.0 g)
180 used in this study were captured from various localities in the northeast of Iran using custom-
181 made mesh live traps (Hamidi et al. 2015). Furthermore, 10 male and 10 female Soori albino
182 house mice (4-week-old and with average weight 26.0 g) and golden hamsters (3-week-old and
183 with average weight 29.0 g) were purchased from Razi Vaccine and Serum Research Institute of
184 Mashhad, Iran. The animals were housed in separate cages in a room with a 12 h light and dark
185 cycle, with temperature of 24-28 °C, and 25-35% humidity. Brush-tailed mice received a variety

186 of seeds and fruits similar to their natural diet whereas mice and golden hamsters were fed with
187 standard mouse feed pellets and water *ad libitum* throughout the experiments. An adult male and
188 female in estrous state (from each species), were coupled with each other for a night, in a cage
189 separately from others. Although there are no data on the estrous cycle for brush-tailed mice,
190 there are some common signs in rodents that are useful in determining when females are in
191 estrous, including holding the tail up, changing in the appearance and color of the vaginal area
192 from pink to reddish, tendency towards males with showing less aggressive manner, and
193 dispersing special smells (Champlin et al. 1973; Marcondes et al. 2002). The following morning,
194 if possible, vaginal smears were prepared and examined under a light microscope to determine
195 the presence of sperms and probable subsequent pregnancy. If pregnancy occurred, counting the
196 embryonic days (E) was started, with E0 indicating the first day after separating female from
197 male. In addition, the animals were observed daily and their body weight was recorded three
198 times a week to verify pregnancy, normal growth and well-being of the embryos. Pregnant
199 females (6 Goodwin's brush-tailed mice, 6 golden hamsters and 8 house mice) were placed in
200 different cages during their pregnancy. Embryos were obtained from euthanized females at days
201 E10-17. Furthermore, newborn pups of each species at different postnatal days (PN) were
202 included in the study (see Hamidi et al. 2018 for details). Animal care and experimental
203 procedures were performed in accordance with the guidelines and protocols approved by the
204 ethics committee of the Rodentology Research Department, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad.

205

206 **Measurements**

207 External measurements of this study including head and body length, tail length, total body
208 length, and hind foot length were taken with a vernier caliper with an accuracy of 0.1 mm. After
209 the birth of newborns, the total body weights of pups were taken daily with an accuracy of 0.1 g
210 and embryo weights were recorded for each stage examined. Data were also recorded on the
211 mean length of the gestation period and on the timing of developmental events including: eye
212 opening, ear eruption, weaning (called as "juvenile" from now on) and starting to feed. These
213 events also correspond with phases of ontogenesis in rodents, such as attainment of the abilities
214 to orient to their environment acoustically or visually and to process solid food. For all recorded
215 values standard deviation (SD) was provided as a measure of the amount of variability or
216 dispersion of the data from the mean.

217

218 **Results**

219 Gestation period in Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse was 31.5 ± 2.1 days on average. The average
220 gestation period in golden hamster was 15.6 ± 0.8 days, which was 5 days shorter than that of the
221 house mouse (20.8 ± 0.8). The average mother's weights prior to parturition were 28 ± 1.4 ,
222 97.8 ± 1.4 and 56.2 ± 1.6 g in Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse, golden hamster, and house mouse,
223 respectively. The reproductive cycle in Goodwin's brush-tailed mice was approximately 1 litter
224 every 9 months. Females in northeastern Iran produce offspring from late winter (in nature) and
225 late autumn (in captivity) until late spring (Hamidi et al. 2015). There are insufficient data for
226 litter size in nature with only a record of two wild females collected in November which had 2
227 and 7 uterine swellings with no visible embryos (Lay 1967). However, the number of young per
228 litter in captivity has been well-studied; captive females generally produced 1 to 5 (3 ± 1.5) young
229 in each parturition (Hamidi et al. 2018). True hamsters and domestic mice reproduce throughout
230 the year and the number of offspring per litter was 8.6 ± 1.5 and 11 ± 2.5 , respectively (Table 1).

231

232 **Morphology and size in prenatal period**

233 At E13, embryos of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse weighed on average 0.2 ± 0.02 g, and total
234 body length measured 7.1 ± 0.1 mm. Ears and eyes were not distinguishable and head and limbs
235 showed very little development (Fig. 1, Table 2). At E14, weight and head and body length were
236 0.3 ± 0.01 g and 9.1 ± 0.2 mm, respectively. Eyes were observed as a dark spot (pigmented optic
237 vesicle) but ears were not completely obvious yet. Tail had grown as a very short appendage, and
238 head development was more than that of limbs (Fig. 1). At E15, weight and head and body
239 length showed 0.2 g (0.5 ± 0.01) and 4 mm (13.1 ± 0.1) increases, respectively. Ears were
240 distinguished and the embryos were miniature newborns (Fig. 1). Embryos at E17, averaged
241 0.7 ± 0.01 g in weight and 19.1 ± 0.1 mm in head and body length. Growth was rapid during the
242 first half of the gestation period (Fig. 2). Up to about E17 the embryos gained as much as
243 0.16 ± 0.01 g/day and 4 ± 0.1 mm/day and after that, in the second half of the gestation period till
244 parturition, their growth rate decreased about half (0.09 g/day and 2.4 mm/day).

245 In the golden hamster, embryos at embryonic day 10 weighed on average 1.2 ± 0.05 g, and head
246 and body length measured 11 ± 0.9 mm. Embryos had distinguishable ears and well-developed
247 pigmented optic vesicles. Shallow grooves indicating the beginning of digit formation were

248 observed on the fore- and hind limbs (Fig. 3 and Table 2). At E13, weight and head and body
249 length were 2.2 ± 0.02 g and 22 ± 0.5 mm, respectively. Fore- and hind limbs showed elongation
250 (Fig. 3). Growth was slow in the first two thirds of the gestation period (up to E10), with
251 embryos gaining only 0.12 ± 0.01 g/day and 1.1 ± 0.09 mm/day. However, in the last third of
252 gestation, embryos grew rapidly at three to four times the rate of the first period for weight and
253 head and body length, respectively (0.32 g/day and 4 mm/day) (Fig. 2).

254 House mouse embryos at E10 weighed on average 0.1 ± 0.09 g and total body length measured
255 6.8 ± 0.2 mm. Embryos had a distinguishable cephalic region, little development of the limbs, but
256 a pronounced tail (Fig. 4). At E13, weight and head and body length were 0.3 ± 0.03 g and 10 ± 0.3
257 mm, respectively. Fore- and hind limbs showed elongation, although faster development of the
258 head as compared with the limbs was observed. Ears and eyes were not clearly distinguishable
259 (Fig. 4 and Table 2). At E14, embryos weighed on average 0.5 ± 0.05 g and head and body length
260 measured 10.4 ± 0.3 mm. External ears were forming and very weak pigmented optic vesicles and
261 shallow grooves indicating the beginning of digit formation could be observed (Fig. 4). At E15,
262 weight and head and body length were 1.1 ± 0.2 g and 17 ± 0.8 mm, respectively. External ear
263 showed further projection with ear canal covered by the pinna (Fig. 4). At E17, embryos weighed
264 on average 1.3 ± 0.2 g and head and body length measured 20.5 ± 0.7 mm with longer fore- and
265 hind limbs having separated digits (Fig. 4). Growth was slow during the first half of the gestation
266 period (Fig. 2). Up to about E10, the embryo gained only 0.01 ± 0.01 g/day and 0.6 ± 0.1 mm/day
267 but after that, in the second half of the gestation period, weight increased rapidly (0.23 g/day)
268 and for head and body length this was at about four times the rate observed in the first half of the
269 gestation period (2.5 mm/day).

270

271 **Morphology and size in postnatal period**

272 At birth, brush-tailed mice, weighed on average 2 ± 0.1 g, had a head and body length of 30 ± 0.8
273 mm (Table 1), and were covered with a very thin and fine coat of dark-colored hair. Ears were
274 separated from the head (Table 2) and the digits of the fore- and hind limbs were separated from
275 each other. By the fifth day, the hair was erect and the dorsal regions of the head, body and tail
276 were generally dark gray, while the pelage of the undersurfaces was white (Table 2 and Fig. 1).

277 The body mass of the newborn was only 10.5% of the adult mass (19.7 ± 0.9 g) and increased to
278 approximately 89.4% of the adult in juveniles (16.7 ± 0.5 g) at PN35. Growth was rapid, the

279 young gaining as much as 0.6 g/day and at 15 days of age had reached 63.1% of the adult weight
280 (12.4±0.5 g). Head and body length in newborns was about 38.9% of the adult length (76.5±1.2
281 mm) but doubled by the juvenile stage. Tail length in the newborn (23±0.8 mm) was
282 approximately 27% of that in adult length (84.5±1.2 mm), reaching 94.1% in juveniles (80±0.6
283 mm). Length growth was more rapid prior to weaning (PN35) as compared to weight (Fig. 2)
284 with 50.7% and 11.9% increase, respectively. After weaning these rates were inversed but rather
285 similar (77.05% and 84.7%, respectively). Differences in the rates of development between the
286 periods of growth from newborn to juvenile and from juvenile to adult were also observed.
287 Although, about a seven times increase was observed in the rate of growth in gaining weight
288 during the periods of growth from newborn to juvenile (11.9%) to from juvenile to adult
289 (84.7%), the rate of growth in the head and body elongation from newborn-juvenile (50.7%) to
290 juvenile-adult (77.05%) showed only about a 1.5% increase (Fig. 2). Length exhibited a different
291 growth pattern (= rate of growth) compared with body weight in the first 20 days, where length
292 rapidly increased but abruptly decreased after this age (Fig. 2 and Table 1). The total length at
293 the age of 20 days was 83.3% (134.2±0.9 mm) of its adult size (162±0.8 mm). Hind foot in
294 newborns (6.8±0.2 mm) was about 33.3% of adult length (21.2±0.5 mm) and grew to 95.2% in
295 juveniles (19.7±0.5 mm). The hind foot grew rapidly during early life reaching its maximum size
296 at 35 days of age. Generally, sexual maturity was not reached at less than 4 months for both
297 males and females. Reproduction in males began at 5 months of age whereas first pregnancy
298 usually occurred in 6-7 month-old females (also see Kilpatrick 2017). Our observations showed
299 that Goodwin's brush-tailed mice are sexually mature when their tail tuft is at least 6 mm long
300 and the hind foot is at least 21 mm.

301 At birth, golden hamsters have a body mass of 2.8±0.07 g, a head and body length of 31.8±0.8
302 mm (Table 1), and eyes that were still covered by a layer of skin (Table 2). Faster development
303 of fore limbs was observed as compared with hind limbs (Fig. 3). The body mass of juveniles at
304 weaning (PN15) was about 24.7% (17.9±0.8 g) of the adult weight with a head and body length
305 of 70.1±0.5 mm (about 46.8% of the adult length) reaching 72.2±0.5 g and 149.6±1.7 mm in
306 adults, respectively. Growth rate of head and body length was rapid (45.6%) both before and
307 after weaning (PN15) as compared with that of weight increase (19.8%). However, no obvious
308 changes were observed in the increasing rate of length in the first two stages of postnatal life
309 (PN0-PN15 and PN15-adult) (see also Table 1 for more details).

310 We found house mouse newborns body mass to average 2.4 ± 0.08 g at birth with a head and body
311 length of 31.4 ± 1.1 mm (Table 1). Separated digits with early formation of claws were visible at
312 the ends of the fore- and hind limbs at this stage (Fig. 4 and Table 2). The body mass of juveniles
313 at weaning (PN16) was 12.7 ± 0.3 g with a head and body length of 64.5 ± 0.9 mm, about 46.1%
314 and 75.2% of the adult weight and length, respectively. In adults, weight averaging 27.5 ± 0.4 g
315 and length was 85.7 ± 0.9 mm. Similar to golden hamster, growth rate of head and body length
316 was rapid (61.8%) both before and after weaning (PN16) as compared with that of weight
317 showing a 32.4% increase. However, approximately two times increases were observed in the
318 growth rates of weight and head and body length in the second stage of postnatal development
319 (PN16-adult) compared with the rates during the first stage (PN0-PN16) (see Table 1 for more
320 details).

321

322 **Discussion**

323 The interaction between duration of pregnancy and developmental rate apparently explains the
324 timing of postnatal life history, indicating that developmental rate and timing parameters govern
325 the entire postnatal period (Zelditch et al. 2003a). There have been several studies on postnatal
326 development of rodents especially model organisms such as house mouse and hamster (e.g.
327 Cardini and O'Higgins 2005; Cubo et al. 2006; Fadda and Leirs 2009; Zoccolan et al. 2009).
328 However, only a few studies have focused on postnatal development of brush-tailed mice (Meyer
329 and Malikov 1996; Volf and Volf 2003, Hamidi et al. 2017b, 2018) and the only study on
330 prenatal development of these rodents focused on tooth morphogenesis (Hamidi et al. 2017b).

331 Herein, we showed that Goodwin's brush-tailed mice are born more developed than either house
332 mice or golden hamsters. With a mean gestation period of 31.5 ± 2.1 days compared with
333 20.8 ± 0.8 days for house mouse and 15.6 ± 0.8 days for golden hamster, newborns of this species
334 have longer time to develop in utero. However, it still takes longer to reach subsequent postnatal
335 milestones (such as weaning) due to a slower rate of development following birth. The ontogeny
336 of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse can be divided into five periods with different growth rates:
337 E0-17, E17-PN0, PN0-PN15/PN20, PN15/PN20-PN35 (juvenile), and PN35 to adulthood. In the
338 first period, prenatal growth is rapid and in the second period it is reduced (Fig. 2). After birth,
339 we observed rapid growth in weight and body length up to PN15 and PN20, respectively.

340 However, in the fourth period growth is slowed down and in the last period growth almost
341 ceases.

342 We observed very rapid prenatal development and also early maturity in golden hamster.
343 Regarding size, little differences were observed among the newborns of the three species at birth.
344 Golden hamsters were the largest species examined, whereas Goodwin's brush-tailed mice and
345 house mice were similar in size but smaller than the golden hamster. Weight and head and body
346 length exhibited different growth rate (and pattern) after birth in the three species examined. In
347 Goodwin's brush-tailed mice the increase in weight was more dynamic than the change in head
348 and body length, up to adulthood. In golden hamster, head and body length showed a stable rate
349 of growth before and after weaning (45.3% as the rate of growth from newborn to juvenile vs.
350 46% as the rate of growth from juvenile to adult), but for body weight, this was slightly more
351 after weaning (15.6% as the rate of growth from newborn to juvenile vs. 24% as the rate of
352 growth from juvenile to adult). For house mouse, weight and head and body length growth were
353 both equally dynamic up to adulthood. For head and body length, the rate of growth from
354 newborn to juvenile was 48.6% vs. 75% as the rate of growth from juvenile to adult. For body
355 weight, 18.8% was indicated as the rate of growth from newborn to juvenile vs. 46% as the rate
356 of growth from juvenile to adult (Fig. 2, see also Table 1). Moreover, the prenatal morphological
357 growth pattern of the house mouse was different from that of the golden hamster, though their
358 postnatal growth patterns were similar (Figs. 1, 3, 4).

359 As found in studies of mammals (O'Higgins et al. 2001; Singleton 2002) and other vertebrates
360 (Monteiro et al. 1997; Zelditch et al. 2003b), even close relatives can differ in their ontogeny. In
361 vertebrates larger size is associated with slower development, later puberty, and lower fecundity
362 (Angelini and Ghiara 1984; Roff 2002). Nevertheless, despite the small size of Goodwin's brush-
363 tailed mouse, tendencies of *K*-selected reproduction are evident in its slow rates of pre- and
364 postnatal development. One can hypothesize that the reproductive pattern observed in
365 *Calomyscus* are due to their derivation from a lineage with this pattern of reproduction, and the
366 genetic makeup of this group is constrained by its phylogenetic history, the genes and genetic
367 pathways that were present in its ancestors rather than being adaptive and the results of selection.
368 However, as we will discuss later, genetic variability can be found in the laboratory "bottle-
369 necked" stock of Goodwin's brush-tailed mice that includes more *r*-selected reproductive
370 characteristics. These observations could be used to reject the null hypothesis of phylogenetic

371 constraint. Hence, it sounds that an adaptation to a particular environment might have a role in
372 such tendency to *K*-reproductive strategy within the genus *Calomyscus*.

373 Members of this genus are generally found in stony or rocky habitats. They are also known to
374 nest in the roots and cavities of oak trees. Furthermore, brush-tailed mice are found in desert
375 regions where they occur beneath dwarf palms (Hamidi et al. 2017a; Kilpatrick 2017). The
376 specialization to such environments requires a number of peculiarities, which are, first of all,
377 mouse-like appearance and a comparatively complicating pattern of locomotion. In *Calomyscus*,
378 locomotion pattern is much more complicating than golden hamster and non-rocky (meadow)
379 voles; they can jump and climb, and use their long tail as a balance, while meadow short-tail
380 voles move like "quadrupedal pouches" (author's observation). It should be mentioned that
381 mouse-like exterior and complicated locomotion seem likely to be based on more prolonged
382 ontogenesis when comparing the forms, which are characterized by the same kind of
383 reproductive strategy. For example, most of the *r*-strategic plain voles are characterized by more
384 rapid kind of postnatal ontogenesis, than *r*-strategic house mouse (Malikov and Meyer 1990).
385 Therefore, we hypothesize that in the case of brush-tailed mice the considerable prolongation of
386 ontogenesis is based on a mouse-like kind of exterior and complicating pattern of locomotion, on
387 one hand, and *K*-reproductive strategy on the other hand. According to Pianka (1970), in such
388 situation "...competition is keen and the optimal strategy is to channel all available matter and
389 energy into maintenance and the production of a few extremely fit offspring".

390 Golden hamster, which is larger than the others in this study, displays a higher tendency to *r*-kind
391 reproductive strategy. Periodic fluctuations of population density is considered as an indicator of
392 *r*-strategy (Krebs and Myers 1974). Nevertheless, there is no evidence about its population
393 fluctuations because it has a very restricted range and appears to be threatened in the wild due to
394 extensive pest control methods and perhaps competition for forage with livestock. Golden
395 hamsters in laboratory conditions exhibit *r*-reproductive strategy (Gattermann et al. 2001).
396 Another indicator can be a tendency to pest activity, which seems to be impossible for small *K*-
397 strategic mammals.

398 The adaptive zones (= ecological niches) related to species of the same genus and closely related
399 genera with rather similar mode of existence (e.g. Ciscaucasian hamster *Mesocricetus raddei*
400 (Nehring, 1894), Turkish hamster *Mesocricetus brandti* (Nehring, 1898), European hamster
401 *Cricetus cricetus* (Linnaeus, 1758)) are characterized by the following features in common: seed

402 diet with a small vegetative quota; solitary mode of existence; spatially continuous habitats
403 within dry steppe zones; evident fluctuations of population density and tendency to crop pest
404 activity (except *Mesocricetus raddei*). Moreover, the introduction of the golden hamster into a
405 laboratory condition also shows an evident potency to *r*-kind of reproduction (Magomedov and
406 Omarov 1995; Surov et al. 2015; Feoktistova et al. 2016). The adaptive zone of the golden
407 hamster is closer to the so-called “perfect ecologic vacuum”, which was characterized by Pianka
408 (1970) as “a lack of density effects and competition”, where “the optimal strategy is to put all
409 possible matter and energy into reproduction, with the smallest practicable amount into each
410 individual offspring, and to produce as many total progenies as possible”.

411 In the golden hamster there is a lack of heterochrony between pre- and postnatal development,
412 both of them were characterized by a higher rate, as compared with the house mouse and
413 especially Goodwin’s brush-tailed mouse. In the house mouse there is an evident heterochrony
414 between pre- and postnatal development. The domestic mouse displayed nearly similar patterns
415 of early prenatal growth and development as Goodwin’s brush-tailed mouse and similar early
416 postnatal growth (up to the end of second week of life) with both Goodwin’s brush-tailed mouse
417 and golden hamster. The house mouse is known to demonstrate the main indicators of *r*-
418 reproductive strategy, fast postnatal development, early sexual maturation, high fecundity and as
419 a result, catastrophic outbreaks of population density (Laurie 1946; Bronson 1979). The benefits
420 of *r*-reproductive strategy for house mouse may be substantial, taking into consideration that its
421 infants are at an exceptionally high risk of mortality (Zelditch et al. 2003a), due to nesting in
422 habitats commensal with humans. Although commensal habitats provide benefits like offering
423 potentially rich food resources, but are also characterized by instability in space and time
424 compared with natural and semi-natural (non-commensal) habitats. Breeding and reproductive
425 rate, survival and mortality rates, migration and dispersal, and flexibility in spatial organization
426 are variables which can be used for testing the hypothesis of great mortality of house mice in
427 anthropogenic habitats than in the wild. According to Pocock et al. (2004) “Non-commensal
428 house mice have lower mortality, seasonal breeding, and individuals move more frequently and
429 further than commensal house mice.” As a whole, Goodwin’s brush-tailed mouse and the house
430 mouse appeared to be rather similar in early morphological development, whereas the golden
431 hamster development was different from these two.

432 Among these three species, Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse displayed a complex *K*-reproductive
433 strategy, where late sexual maturation (not earlier than 4 months) is a direct consequence of a
434 slow prenatal and subsequent postnatal development. However, in the laboratory "bottle-necked"
435 stock of Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse approximately 20% of individuals opened their eyes on
436 the 12th day of life (Meyer and Malikov 1996) and 1 female out of 20 (5%) produced 1 litter per
437 month for half a year, which reveals a cryptic potential of more *r*-reproductive characteristics in
438 this species. The "bottle-neck" effect is inevitable when only a few parental individuals from
439 natural genetically polymorphic population give an origin to the laboratory stock. Such stock
440 inevitably has a much reduced genetic variation, that can "open the road to phenotype" to some
441 characters, which are not revealed in enough polymorphic populations. In the case of brush-
442 tailed mice, which are *K*-strategic in the wild or in nature, in their laboratory stock there were
443 some characters of *r*-reproductive strategy, as mentioned above.

444 All the reproductive and developmental elements of the golden hamster are *r*-strategic kind,
445 while some elements of *r*-strategic *Mus musculus* development are closer to the *K*-strategic
446 *Calomyscus*. In the golden hamster pre- and postnatal development, including the sexual
447 maturation, are comparatively rapid. We propose that this species is a good example of a basic
448 evolutionary shift towards *r*-reproductive strategy, at both pre- and postnatal levels. With regard
449 to *r*-reproductive strategy of the house mouse, it presumably was not completely "turned on" at
450 the level of prenatal development. In that form of life, the initial association between pre- and
451 postnatal development was considerably "broken up". As a result, house mouse combines
452 comparatively slow episodes of prenatal development with rapid postnatal development and *r*-
453 kind of reproduction (Rugh 1968; Kotenkova and Priluzskaya 1994).

454 Previous studies (Malikov and Meyer 1990; Meyer and Malikov 1996) have revealed several
455 facts on fecundity and postnatal ontogenesis of voles (Cricetidae: Arvicolinae) with *r*- or *K*-
456 reproductive tendencies including data on intraspecific variants and extremes of fecundity
457 (maximal litter size and minimal age of a pregnant female) in laboratory stocks of voles species
458 *Chionomys nivalis* (Martins, 1842) (European snow vole), *Chionomys gud* Satunin, 1909
459 (Caucasian snow vole) and *Chionomys roberti* (Thomas, 1906) (Robert's snow vole) which could
460 serve as potentially raw materials for evolutionary shifts of reproductive strategy. Among voles
461 the stenobiotic species, which normally show the *K*-reproductive strategy, are strictly associated
462 with fragmentary habitats of a particular kind. They are, for example, such alpine species of the

463 genus *Chionomys*, as European snow vole and Caucasian snow vole, which in contrast to
464 lowland meadow or steppe vole species of comparatively continuous habitats, live only in rocky
465 areas. The laboratory stocks of those stenobiotic alpine species of the genus *Chionomys*
466 displayed comparatively slower postnatal development (eyes opening on 11th-13th day, and the
467 first pregnancy no earlier than the third month) than the lowland ones, but the same duration of
468 pregnancy (20 days) (Malikov and Meyer 1990). Therefore, they presumably have similar
469 patterns of prenatal development with species living in lowland. The laboratory stocks of
470 lowland non-stenobiotic vole species, which show evident fluctuations of population density in
471 nature, were characterized by a typical *r*-kind of reproduction (capacity of producing a litter per
472 20 days for several months and a high rate of postnatal development (eyes opening on 9th-10th
473 day, and the first pregnancy mainly in 3 month old females) (Malikov and Meyer 1990). In the
474 stenobiotic European snow vole (*Chionomys nivalis*), approximately 25% of females in their
475 “bottle-necked” laboratory stock, demonstrated a tendency to more or less *r*-reproduction
476 (Malikov and Meyer 1990). In addition to these examples of reproductive flexibility, it has been
477 reported that such typically *r*-strategic voles such as the bank vole *Myodes glareolus* (Schreber
478 1780) can produce either *r*- or *K*-reproductive cohorts dependent on environmental conditions
479 (Olenev 2002).

480

481 **Conclusion**

482 According to Creighton and Strauss (1986), differences in the length of gestation, postnatal
483 growth rate, and duration of growth might reflect relative selection on life history traits or may
484 represent differences due to phylogenetic history. The results of our study showed possibility of
485 both scenarios. In the golden hamster, and likely all true hamsters, rapid growth and
486 development in both pre- and postnatal stages is hypothesized to be the results of their quite
487 ancient occupation of an adaptive zone, where the tendency to *r*-kind of reproduction was the
488 most optimal. For house mouse, considering the high risk of mortality and other topics
489 mentioned earlier, heterochrony observed between pre- and postnatal development as well as *r*-
490 reproductive strategy provides lots of benefits. In contrast, long term development and tendency
491 to *K*-reproductive strategy in brush-tailed mice probably have resulted in better survival due to
492 living in discontinuous habitats with usually difficult environmental conditions and limited food

493 resources which can threaten them. In addition, *r*- or *K*-kind of fecundity can be switched on
494 epigenetically by different environmental conditions, as was shown by Olenev (2002).

495 Developmental patterns and their phenotypic endpoints reflect the ecological history of the taxa
496 studied. Now, while looking back to the basic “*Evo-Devo*” approach, according to which the
497 evolutionary changes mainly do not happen in adults, being the results of shifts in ontogenetic
498 pathways, it is getting clear that the strategy of reproduction is characterized by a high flexibility
499 of maintenance, with following approaches: 1) developmental self-consistence, where
500 reproduction strategy is directly determined by pre- and postnatal development of either slow (*K*)
501 (in Goodwin’s brush-tailed mouse) or fast (*r*) (in golden hamster) kind, 2) heterochrony, where
502 some episodes of prenatal development are hypothesized to be ontogenetic rudiments of
503 historically reproductive strategy, whereas an alternative strategy is hypothesized to result
504 primarily from postnatal adaptations (such as in *Mus* and *Chionomys*), and finally, 3) epigenetic
505 switching on the reproduction of either *r*- or *K*-kind (*Myodes* and obviously most of the non-
506 stenobiotic voles and lemmings) (Olenev, 2002).

507 In summary, our results demonstrate that despite external similarities at birth between
508 Goodwin’s brush-tailed mouse, golden hamster and house mouse, they manifest some evident
509 developmental differences at pre- and postnatal periods. These differences might provide clues to
510 evolutionary modeling the *r*- or *K*-reproduction maintenance. Such speculations, however, awaits
511 further experimental investigations.

512 Comparison of the developmental process and growth data of different species of brush-tailed
513 mice is suggested for a better inference of speciation and habitat specialization in this group.
514 Cladistics analyses on various morphological and morphometric characters during the pre- and
515 postnatal development of different species of Calomyscidae, identifying intraspecific
516 polymorphisms as well as synapomorphies for the family, comprehensive evolutionary
517 comparative studies on different characters of this basal group and other muroid rodents, and
518 also extracting plesiomorphic characters will be informative for exact determination of
519 evolutionary pathway of these rodents, which are an early diverging clade of the Eumuroida,
520 based on *Evo-Devo* approach.

521

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528

529 **Compliance with ethical standards**

530 **Conflict of interest** The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

531

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536

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539 were in accordance with the ethical standards of Ferdowsi University of Mashhad.

540

541 **Author contributions**

542 KH designed the study, collected the samples and conducted laboratory procedures, wrote the
543 manuscript and provided the figures. MMM conducted the methodology and inferences, and also
544 had valuable discussions about the content. JD conceived and designed the study, and also
545 stimulated the interest in brush-tailed mice study. VGM had valuable discussions about the
546 content. All authors contributed in proofreading.

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552

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701

702

703 **Table legend**

704 **Table 1** Comparative reproductive features of Goodwin’s brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus*
 705 *elburzensis*), golden hamster (*Mesocricetus auratus*) and house mouse (*Mus musculus*). Some
 706 parts reproduced from Suckow et al. (2000), Volf and Volf (2003), Banks et al. (2010) and
 707 Hamidi et al. (2017b, 2018) shown in italic are indicated with ■, ♦, ●, *, and **, respectively. For
 708 all recorded values standard deviation (SD) is provided.

Developmental characteristic	Species		
	<i>Calomyscus elburzensis</i>	<i>Mesocricetus auratus</i> (Lab race)	<i>Mus musculus</i> (Lab race)
Age of sexual maturity	<i>Not less than 4 months of age for both females and males **</i>	<i>Females at 6 weeks of age and males at 8 weeks ●</i>	<i>Females at about 6 weeks of age and males at about 8 weeks ■</i>
Length of the gestation period (day)	<i>31.5±2.1 *</i>	<i>15.6±0.8 *</i>	<i>20.8±0.8 *</i>
Mean number of litters/year	One litter every 9 months	Every month throughout the year	Throughout the year; 5 to 10 litters per year
Mean number of young/litter	3±1.5	8.6±1.5	11±2.5
Size (weight, and head and body length) of newborns	<i>2±0.1 g **, 30±0.8 mm</i>	<i>2.8±0.07 g, 31.8±0.8 mm</i>	<i>2.4±0.08 g, 31.4±1.1 mm</i>
Size (weight, and head and body length) of juveniles (at weaning)	<i>16.7±0.5 g, 59.1±0.3 mm</i>	<i>17.9±0.8 g, 70.1±0.5 mm</i>	<i>12.7±0.3 g, 64.5±0.9 mm</i>
Size (weight, and head and body length) of adults	<i>19.7±0.9 g, 76.5±1.2 mm</i>	<i>72.2±0.5 g, 149.6±1.7 mm</i>	<i>27.5±0.4 g, 85.7±0.9 mm</i>
Length of life span in	<i>Generally between 4</i>	<i>Mean 2-3 years, up to</i>	<i>Normally for about 2</i>

captivity	<i>to 5 years ** but there are records indicating that they can live as long as 9 years in captivity</i> ♦	4 years •	<i>to 3 years but up to 5 years is also recorded</i> ■
Reproductive strategy	Tendency to <i>K</i> -kind	A typical <i>r</i> -kind	A typical <i>r</i> -kind

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733 **Table 2** Major events in the pre- and postnatal developmental stages of Goodwin’s brush-tailed
 734 mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*), golden hamster (*Mesocricetus auratus*) and house mouse (*Mus*
 735 *musculus*). E and PN indicate the average embryonic and postnatal days, respectively. Parts
 736 shown in italic are reproduced from Hamidi et al. (2018).

Developmental stage	Developmental feature	Species		
		<i>Calomyscus elburzensis</i>	<i>Mesocricetus auratus</i> (Lab race)	<i>Mus musculus</i> (Lab race)
Prenatal period	Forming of limbs	E15	Before E10	E13
	Distinguishing of ears	E15	Before E10	E14
	Distinguishing of fingers	E15	Before E10	E14
	Miniature newborn	E15	Before E10	E14
	Separation of ears from the head	<i>PN0</i>	PN3	PN2
	Emerging of thin hairs	PN1	PN2	PN2
	Primary erecting of hairs	PN3	PN4	PN4
	Opening of eyes	<i>PN15</i>	PN14	PN13
Postnatal period	Feeding on hard foods	After about PN24	PN14	PN14
	Weaning	<i>At about PN35</i>	PN15	PN16
	Beginning to explore outside the nest	<i>At about PN35</i>	PN15	PN15
	Miniature adult	After PN35 (when tail tuft appears)	PN15	PN15

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741 **Figure captions**

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 743 **Fig. 1** *Calomyscus elburzensis* at embryonic days (E) 13, 14, 15, 17 and at postnatal days (PN) 0,
 744 10, 15 and 20. E13: a distinguishable cephalic region (Cr), not distinguishable ears and eyes,
 745 formation of fore- and hind limbs (FL and HL, respectively). E14: weak pigmented optic vesicle
 746 (Ov), slightly pronounced tail (T). Head development was more than that of limbs. E15: forming
 747 external ear (Ee) and ear canal covered by the pinna. Shallow grooves indicating the beginning
 748 of digit formation (D). The vascularization (V) was visible over the body due to little skin
 749 pigmentation. E17: peripheral vessels (V) can be observed through the thin skin, longer
 750 forelimbs and hind limbs with separated digits (D). PNO: a marked change in skin pigmentation,
 751 with a darker dorsal region (Dr) and lighter ventral region (Vr), further projected external ear
 752 (Ee), well-developed nasal region (Nr) and vibrissae. Separated digits with early formation of
 753 claws were visible at the ends of the fore- and hind limbs (D). PN10: the eyes were still covered
 754 by a layer of skin (E), deeper grooves were visible between the digits (D). PN15: opening of eyes
 755 (E). PN20: individuals exhibited similar features to neonates, with elongated, well-developed
 756 bodies and longer tails (except in the tail tuft) (T). Scale bars indicate 5 mm in upper row and 10
 757 mm in lower row.

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759 **Fig. 2** Growth curves of Goodwin’s brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*), golden
 760 hamster (*Mesocricetus auratus*) and house mouse (*Mus musculus*) during pre- and postnatal
 761 development. Changes in body weight (a), and head and body length (b) are shown for different
 762 E and PN, indicate the average embryonic and postnatal days, respectively. In Goodwin’s brush-
 763 tailed mouse prenatal growth was rapid at first half of gestation period (up to about E17) and
 764 after that, it grew slowly. Postnatal growth rate of head and body length was considerably rapid
 765 before weaning (PN35) as compared with that of weight, but this was inversed after weaning.
 766 Although, great increases were observed in the growth rate of weight, growth rate of head and
 767 body length during PN35 to adult showed little increase. In golden hamster, prenatal growth was
 768 slow at first two thirds of gestation period (up to E10) and after that, it grew rapidly. Postnatal
 769 growth rate of head and body length was rapid both before and after weaning (PN15) as
 770 compared with that of weight. However, no obvious changes were observed in the increasing rate
 771 of length in the first two stages of postnatal life (PN0-PN15 and PN15-adult). In house mouse,
 772 prenatal growth was slow at first half of gestation period (up to about E10) and after that, it grew
 773 rapidly. Postnatal growth rate of head and body length was rapid both before and after weaning
 774 (PN16) as compared with that of weight. However, increasing was observed in the growth rate of
 775 both weight and length of body in the second stage of postnatal life (PN16-adult) as compared
 776 with the first one (PN0-PN16).

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 779 **Fig. 3** *Mesocricetus auratus* at embryonic days (E) 10 and 13 and at postnatal days (PN) 0, 10,
 780 15 and 20. E10: well development of pigmented optic vesicle (Ov), distinguishable external ear
 781 (Ee), developed fore- and hind limbs (FL and HL, respectively). Shallow grooves indicating the
 782 beginning of digit formation (D). The vascularization (V) was visible over the body due to little
 783 skin pigmentation. E13: longer fore- and hind limbs (FL and HL, respectively). PN0: the eyes
 784 were still covered by a layer of skin (E), faster development of fore limbs (FL) as compared with
 785 hind limbs (HL). PN10: the eyes were still closed (E), deeper grooves were visible between the
 786 digits (D). PN15: weaning. PN20: individuals exhibited completely similar features to neonates.
 787 Scale bars indicate 5 mm in upper row and 10 mm in lower row.

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 791 **Fig. 4** *Mus musculus* at embryonic days (E) 10, 13, 14, 15, 17 and at postnatal days (PN) 0, 10,
 792 15 and 20. E10: a distinguishable cephalic region (Cr), little development in fore- and hind limbs
 793 (FL and HL, respectively), pronounced tail (T). E13: longer fore- and hind limbs (FL and HL,
 794 respectively), not clearly distinguishable ears and eyes, faster development in the head as
 795 compared with the limbs. E14: very weak pigmented optic vesicle (Ov), forming external ear
 796 (Ee). Shallow grooves indicating the beginning of digit formation (D). E15: further projected
 797 external ear (Ee), and ear canal covered by the pinna. The peripheral vessels (V) were visible
 798 over the body due to little skin pigmentation. E17: longer fore- and hind limbs (FL and HL,
 799 respectively) with separated digits. PN0: Separated digits with early formation of claws were
 800 visible at the ends of the fore- and hind limbs (FL and HL, respectively), skin pigmentation,
 801 further formation of pigmented optic vesicle (Ov). PN10: the eyes were still covered by a layer
 802 of skin (E), deeper grooves were visible between the digits (D). PN15: feeding on hard foods
 803 (such as corn) (arrow) and near to weaning. PN20: individuals exhibited completely similar
 804 features to neonates, with elongated, well-developed bodies and longer tails (T). Scale bars
 805 indicate 5 mm in upper row and 10 mm in lower row.

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